

PRINCIPLE OF RELATIONSHIP OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION WITH PERSONAL PRACTICE

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Some scientists see the main function of physical culture and sports in eliminating the constraints of modern life with their help. But there is another point of view - that physical education is designed to prepare people who are able to work highly productively and selflessly defend their homeland from the attacks of enemies.

This gives the principle of linking physical education with the practice of life new content and meaning. In the implementation of this principle of physical education, it is necessary to proceed from the fact that everywhere, ultimately, preparation for work and defense should be taken into account.[1,56]

There is an opinion that the applied value of physical education is only in the development of motor skills that are directly necessary in life. If the skill formed as a result of practicing this or that type of physical exercise is applied, i.e. can be transferred to a working or combat

ABSTRACT

This principle expresses the main social regularity of physical education, its main service function is to prepare people for activity, for life. In all systems of physical education, this pattern has its own specific expression.

situation, then such physical education is associated with life.

The goal is that, having come to production or the army, a person in the shortest possible time can master the technique of any business. Only a strong, dexterous and physically developed person is better at mastering a new job, mastering a new technique faster.[4,252]

The modern practice of combat training of troops shows that the more complex military equipment, the deeper and more versatile the requirements for the physical fitness of people should be. The tasks of special military-applied training are put forward in a prominent place.

Some scientists pose the question - what is more important for life: a motor skill or physical qualities, the education of which should be provided in the process of physical education? This question is inappropriate in this formulation. Quality and skill do not exist in isolation from each other. This formulation of the question

practically leads to the opposition of education to upbringing and vice versa. Both are important. A person prepared for life is a person with a high level of development of physical qualities and a large supply of various motor skills. Together, both of these factors guarantee the physical fitness necessary for life.[5,23] Physical education should ensure an appropriate level of health of members of society, the development of their strength and endurance. The principle of the connection between physical education and the practice of life should be guided by all particular tasks of physical education, including sports training, including physical exercises that have a direct applied value.

As a result, the following concretizing provisions of the principle of connection of

physical education with the practice of life can be derived:

1. solving specific problems of physical training, all other things being equal, one should give preference to those means (physical exercises) that form vital motor skills and skills of a direct labor character;
2. in any form of physical activity, it is necessary to strive to ensure the acquisition of the widest possible fund of various motor skills and abilities, as well as the all-round development of physical abilities;
3. constantly and purposefully link cultural activities with the formation of an active life position of the individual but on the basis of the education of industriousness, patriotism and moral qualities.[6,23]

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